

FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF RISK MANAGEMENT IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the factors affecting the financial performance and ROE of commercial banks using an econometric approach, and the possibilities of artificial intelligence in improving risk management are substantiated. The results of multifactorial logarithmic regression showed that digitalization and GDP growth increase profitability, while problem loans decrease it. It was confirmed that machine learning and "big data" methods are effective in reducing credit risks and strengthening the stability of banks.

Commercial banks face various and multifaceted risks in their daily financial and economic activities. Each type of banking risk differs in terms of its source of occurrence, the scale of the potential threat to financial stability, and the consequences it poses for the bank if the risk materializes. It is worth noting that one of the main trends in banking in the current decade is the introduction of intelligent systems to improve existing risk management. This is explained, first of all, by the rapid development of artificial intelligence and its active penetration into all business processes of the bank. On the one hand, in the current conditions, the introduction of modern intelligent technologies is becoming an important competitive advantage in the activities of commercial banks. However, on the other hand, this process is also causing the emergence of new types of threats associated with the introduction of artificial intelligence systems. Although modern technologies have significantly simplified many routine business processes and allowed commercial banks to focus on strategic tasks, even the most advanced artificial intelligence systems remain vulnerable to operational risks to a certain extent. Therefore, financial institutions are required to use innovative technologies with caution and a thorough approach.

To date, domestic and CIS economists have always been engaged in the problems of bank risk management and their improvement. In particular, the principles of management in the activities of commercial banks and areas of their improvement have found expression in the scientific research of leading foreign economists D.J. Siynki, U. Koch Timoti [1], I.V. Larionova [2] and others.

The activities of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan, their tasks and some theoretical and practical aspects of managing the development of commercial banks, the

existing problems in this system were studied by economists B.T. It was studied in the scientific works of Berdiyarov [3], V.A. Kotov [4], I.L. Butikov, N.Kh. Jumaev [5], O.B. Sattarov [6].

Every year, the number of factors that need to be taken into account to accurately assess a borrower's credit rating is increasing. These factors include not only financial indicators, such as income level, but also many non-financial factors. In particular, indicators such as the client's business reputation, the presence of late payments, the borrower's family composition, the number of children, the structure of transactions on bank accounts significantly complicate the credit assessment process. It has become practically impossible for bank employees to analyze these numerous parameters qualitatively and quickly.[2] As a result, without the introduction of artificial intelligence systems, the time for responding to loan applications would have been significantly longer, and the quality of the assessment would not have been high enough.[3]

The results show that the increase in the volume of digital banking operations has a significant positive impact on ROE: respectively, the coefficient is positive and greater than unity, indicating that digitalization processes in banking are increasing the return on capital by reducing costs, increasing transaction speed and enhancing service efficiency. Similarly, the growth of the country's GDP has a strong multiplicative effect on the profitability of banks, and macroeconomic stability, business activity and the expansion of lending volumes serve to improve financial results. The increase in the number of users of digital services also has a positive elasticity, which means that the expansion of the customer base through remote banking services, mobile applications and fintech platforms increases banks' non-interest income and operational efficiency. Conversely, an increase in the volume of problem loans was found to have a negative impact on ROE, since poor-quality assets in the loan portfolio increase the need for provisioning, reduce profit margins and limit the effective use of capital.

In times of economic instability, a fraction of a second in concluding a transaction in financial markets can be crucial. Therefore, such artificial intelligence systems allow a bank to significantly reduce the likelihood of market risks, since time delays in executing transactions can lead to multi-million dollar financial losses.[5]

Another relevant tool based on artificial intelligence and being introduced into the bank's risk management system are intelligent risk hedging systems. These algorithms are used to develop a bank's market risk hedging strategies and serve to protect a commercial bank from unexpected adverse market fluctuations. The tasks solved by such systems include making decisions on the purchase or sale of derivative financial instruments - in particular, options and futures - depending on the forecasted changes in market conditions.

As part of stress testing with the help of artificial intelligence, commercial banks can solve a number of important tasks. In particular, it is possible to forecast scenarios such as a sharp outflow of deposits, changes in interest rates, the introduction of sanctions against the financial system and assess their impact on bank liquidity. Such stress-modeling capabilities are provided by advanced SI tools based on deep learning algorithms, such as TensorFlow and PyTorch. These technologies allow for rapid forecasting of changes in bank liquidity, taking into account customer behavior or changes in market conditions.[7]

The results of the above econometric analyses clearly demonstrate that the financial stability and return on capital of commercial banks largely depend on the level of credit risk and digital transformation indicators. In particular, according to the results of the regression

model, it was found that an increase in the volume of problem loans (NPL) has a negative impact on ROE and reduces the financial efficiency of banks, while, on the contrary, an increase in the level of digital transactions and the use of digital services by customers significantly increases profitability. The closeness of the distribution of residuals to the normal form confirms the statistical reliability of the model and the empirical validity of the identified relationships. These results indicate the need to further improve risk management processes in banking. From this point of view, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) methods in the banking risk management system is of strategic importance. Unlike traditional assessment mechanisms, AI technologies allow for real-time processing of large volumes of data, identification of hidden patterns, and advance forecasting of credit risks. In particular, machine learning algorithms help reduce NPL levels by automating credit scoring, accurately assessing customer solvency, and identifying the likelihood of default at an early stage. Neural networks and big data analysis also serve as effective tools for detecting fraudulent transactions, monitoring liquidity risks, and optimizing portfolio diversification.

Summarizing the results of the study, a number of important aspects can be highlighted. First of all, in modern economic conditions, commercial banks are increasingly faced with more and more types of risks in their daily activities. This situation increases the need to form an effective risk management system in order to ensure financial stability and competitiveness. Traditional risk management methods are becoming increasingly inadequate due to the transformation of the conditions of financial market activity. Therefore, banks have become leading subjects of digital business transformation and are introducing dozens of new solutions and systems based on artificial intelligence.

References:

- 1.Тимоти У. Кох. Управление банком: пер. с англ. В 5-ти томах (книгах), 6-ти частях. Уфа: Спектр. Часть 1,2003. - 112 с.;
- 2.Ларионова И.В. Управление активами и пассивами в коммерческом банке. - М.: Консалтбанкир, 2003. - 272 с.;
- 3.Berdiyarov B.T. Profitability of asset operations of commercial banks. Abstract of the dissertation written for the degree of candidate of economic sciences. - Tashkent. BMA. 2002. - 21 p.;
- 4.Kotov V.A. Organization of the securities market. -Т. "Finance" 2007.; Butikov IL. The securities market of Uzbekistan: problems of formation and development. Т.: "KOK8A1L)1TSHF0KM KA8NK" 2008.;
- 5.Jumayev N.Kh., Abdurakhmonov O.K. The world financial and economic crisis: causes and problems of its elimination. - Т.: Akabepshazbg, 2010. - 160 p.;
- 6.Sattorov O.B. Improving the provision of liquidity of commercial banks. Dissertation abstract for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences. - Tashkent, BMA, 2008. - 21 p.